

Future Animal Protein Availability in Turkey: Perspectives and Factors Influencing a Sustainable Equilibrium

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Abstract

Due to rising temperatures and increased air pollutants, Turkey, like the rest of the world, is facing climate change that is profoundly affecting its agricultural sector. This situation is aggravated by the aging of the rural population, demographic pressures, and significant immigration from neighboring countries. Despite the expansion of areas dedicated to livestock, the production of animal proteins remains insufficient to meet the growing demand. This study investigated the availability of animal protein in Turkey, projecting the situation to 2030 using Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models. Various data, encompassing greenhouse gas emission, climatic, economic, and social factors, were collected from sources such as the World Bank and the United Nations Food and Agriculture Databases. Even if Turkey currently meets its animal protein needs, future scenarios may differ. Predictions indicate a potential decline in protein availability at the individual level over the next decade due to climatic conditions, atmospheric and environmental pollutants, social factors, and the level of animal protein production. Projections suggest that the daily consumption of animal protein per individual could drop below 15 g/day. Therefore, it becomes imperative to explore alternative sources of protein such as protein from legumes and plant seeds. Additionally, other options, such as protein derived from grains and oilseeds, are considered key sources of plant-based protein. Projections suggest that the daily consumption of animal protein per individual could drop below 15 g/day.

Keywords: *animal protein, availability, food security, forecasting, Turkey.*

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Introduction

The terrestrial and aquatic animal husbandry sectors play a central role in the economies of developing countries (Pangui, & Kaboret, 2013). Livestock farming constitutes 30% of the gross domestic product of agriculture (Yisehak, 2010) and contributes to poverty reduction in developing countries (McDermott, et al., 2010; Poulain, & Mollier, 2011). Asia, for example, alone holds 89% of world aquaculture production (Grainger, et al., 2012). Fish is one of the most traded staple foods in the world (Grainger, et al., 2012). All these agricultural and fishing activities have undergone changes in the last decades to rapidly increase the supply and meet an ever-increasing demand, due to the increase in world population and higher needs for animal protein (Grainger, et al., 2012; Delgado, et al., 1999). This trend will continue over the next few years, especially in developing countries, and this will not be without consequences for the livelihoods of smallholders, on human and animal health, and on the environment (Cleaver, & Ganguly, 2005).

In several developing countries, protein of animal origin represents 15 to 25% of dietary protein (Grainger, et al., 2012). A healthy, adequate, and balanced diet is only possible with an adequate protein intake. The recommended daily protein intake for adults varies between 0.8 and 1.6% of body weight, depending on age, physical activity, and physiological state (Mehmet, & Hayriye, 2022). In addition, the nutritional value of animal protein is higher than that of vegetable protein (Miassi, et al., 2022). For example, the contribution of fish products to animal protein intake is 19.2% (Grainger, et al., 2012). Two thirds of the total consumption of fishery products occurs in Asia (20.7 kg per inhabitant), being the main source of animal protein, with China topping the list.

Despite this commendable effort by some countries, the question of how the planet will meet the protein needs of the world population in the decades to come is often debated in contemporary debates (Aiking, & De Boer, 2020; Nijdam, Rood, & Westhoek, 2012). In the current state of things, it is proving impossible to meet the announced needs, because despite the increase in funding for agricultural research, approximately one person in seven suffers from chronic malnutrition (Foley, et al., 2011; De Schutter, & Vanloqueren, 2011). Moreover, by 2050, when the population is expected to reach nearly 9.8 billion inhabitants, a 119% increase in food production would be necessary if agricultural systems do not evolve to the detriment of the areas reserved for animal production (Berners-Lee, et al., 2018; FAO, 2022). However, the decrease in foods of animal origin (meat, fish, dairy products, and eggs) can lead to a decrease in protein intake in terms of quality and quantity (Stenson, & Buttriss, 2020; Allison, et al., 2006). Additionally, concerns may also arise regarding certain micronutrients (e.g., zinc, vitamin B12, and fatty acids) if they are replaced with plant-based foods (Leroy, & Cofnas, 2020).

The link mentioned between the accessibility of a source of protein and the level of its consumption results in the relative proportions of the different sources of animal protein varying according to the continents (FAO, 2022). As Gliessman, (2006) puts it, “the problem is not with the animals themselves, but rather with how they are integrated into agro-ecosystems and food systems”. Even if current agricultural models theoretically have the capacity to meet global protein needs, they fail to do so for several reasons: (i) the poorest people’s lack of access to food resources, (ii) inefficiencies and losses of production systems in terms of storage and processing, and (iii) food waste (Wattiaux, 2017). Thus, the animal feed production industry generates a considerable demand for water to produce cereals and fodder intended for animal feed (FAO, 2020). This intensive use of water, often in areas where water resources are already limited, exacerbates the problems associated with water scarcity in some regions. Under the current system and using simplified and conservative models, refs. Ismail, et al., (2020) and Pelletier, & Tyedmers, (2010) estimated that by 2050, greenhouse gas emissions from livestock activities and the production of meat, milk, and eggs would increase over the years, which would not be without impact on the meat and fish production sectors. Therefore, access to animal protein can be a problem not only

in underdeveloped countries but also for socio-economic groups and the elderly population in developed countries (Berner, et al., 2013).

In Turkey, a country that mainly spans the Asian continent, the level of consumption of animal products such as red meat, fish, and milk is lower than that recorded in developed countries (Mehmet, & Hayriye, 2022). This is explained by the high input costs for red meat, the diversity of consumption habits, and the seasonal characteristics of milk and fish supplies (Can, Günlü, & Can, 2015; Can, 2018; Ozen, Tekindal, & Mustafa, 2019; Turkstat, 2021). It is therefore important to consider strategies now to ensure that Turkish populations have access to these sources of protein in the decades to come. There are many economic and political technologies to eliminate protein deficiencies. Perhaps the most interesting of these solutions would be the artificial (in vitro) production of meat (Mehmet, & Hayriye, 2022). However, this solution is still controversial from an ethical point of view (Lee, et al., 2020; Surek, & Uzun, 2020). It is in this context that this study proposes to investigate the prediction of animal protein availability in Turkey by 2030.

Moreover, the choice to conduct this study on animal proteins in general in Turkey is based on a significant gap in the existing research. In analyzing the previous scientific literature, very few studies have been undertaken to comprehensively examine the consumption and nutritional implications of animal protein in this specific context. Indeed, it is important to note that the few studies that have looked at this topic in Turkey have mainly focused on red meat, with an emphasis on species such as beef, pork, lamb, and others. These include, for example, the work of Akgül, & Yildiz, (2016); Çelik, (2012); Gunaydin, (2007); Yavuz, & Zulauf, (2004). These studies neglected to include other important sources of animal protein, such as poultry, fish, dairy products, and eggs, which are also an integral part of the Turkish diet. Therefore, our study aims to comprehensively fill this gap by examining the entire spectrum of animal protein, thus providing a more comprehensive and accurate understanding of dietary habits and the nutritional impact of animal protein in Turkey.

The overall objective was to analyze the availability and current demand and to forecast the demand for animal proteins by 2030. Concretely, it was first a question of analyzing the evolution of climatic and demographic factors, areas occupied, and animal protein demands over time. Next was identifying the parameters determining the availability of animal proteins, and finally, predicting the impacts of the various parameters on the availability of animal proteins by 2030 while identifying the risks, constraints, and opportunities that this may present.

Methodology

Justification for the Choice of the Study Area

Turkey is a transcontinental country with a small part of its population aligned with Europe (5%) and the large part with Asia (95%) (Maeva, 2008); which gives it great geographical and climatic diversity. The choice of this country in such a study therefore makes it possible to study simultaneously the impact of varied environmental conditions on the production and availability of animal proteins on two different continents. Moreover, being a country with a large population, the 18th most populated nation according to the Ministry of Europe and Foreign Affairs (MEFA, 2023), a study of the availability of animal proteins in this country makes it possible to consider demographic factors, political food industries, economic constraints, and consumption trends that can influence the availability of animal protein. Finally, the choice of this country is also and above all justified by its position at the world level when we talk about its level of animal production, especially sheep where Turkey is considered 6th at the world level and 3rd for milk production (Thevenin, 2015). A study predicting the availability of animal protein in a country where livestock farming occupies a prominent place provides a better understanding of the issues related to its sustainability.

Figure 1 shows the map of the study area (Turkey) as a whole.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area (Turkey)

Data Collection

To better predict the dynamics around the availability of proteins of animal origin, data have been collected and exploited. These data include climatic, economic, and social data. Indeed, among the climatic parameters which have been exploited we find precipitation, temperature, and atmospheric pollutants considered as climatic elements with decisive effects on the livestock sector (Diallo, Barry, & Weibigue, 2021). Thus, the variability around these parameters generates thermal stress and increases the mortality rate in the event of an increase in them, particularly regarding temperature and pollutants (Diallo, Barry, & Weibigue, 2021). The same applies to atmospheric pollutants such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

Data on temperature and precipitation were collected over a period ranging from (1990–2020) on the World Bank (WB) site while data related to pollutants were collected on the United Nations site, Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO).

Furthermore, data relating to economic factors such as the annual price of a ton of animal protein and the gross annual income per capita are also determining factors in the accessibility of animal protein (Caillavet, Fadhuile, & Nichèle, 2019; FAO, 2017). In addition to the climatic (temperature, precipitation, and pollutants) and economic parameters (in particular, the gross annual income per inhabitant and the price of a tonne of animal protein), the population explosion also remains a major factor in the availability of resources of animal origin (Caillavet, Fadhuile, & Nichèle, 2019). Data on Turkish population density and economic parameters (price and income per capita) were also collected for the same period from 1990 to 2020 on the FAO website.

In addition to the various factors previously described, the study considered other parameters such as land occupation for both agriculture and grazing (permanent and temporary). The choice of these variables is associated with the fact that agricultural and animal production complement each other and

exploit a common resource which is land. Thus, the occupation of land for agricultural production and grazing sometimes generates conflicts between herders and farmers (Blanc, 2022). However, it is also accepted that animal husbandry could mitigate environmental impacts on soils through the input of organic manure from animals (FAO, 2023), while produce from farmland is used to feed livestock (CIRAD, 2023). In addition, it is important to specify that the various data were collected at the level of the various sites mentioned in the period from the end of July 2023.

Analysis Method

The evaluation of the different variables on which the data were collected was carried out using time series techniques, as several authors Hoang, et al., (2014) and Badameli, & Dubreuil, (2015) have done in their previous studies. These techniques made it possible to describe and explain the evolution of each variable during the observation time interval considered.

Predictions were made using Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models. They represent the most used method in the case of time series, insofar as ARIMA models are designed to represent the behavior of processes subjected to random shocks over time (Saki, 2016). This is the case of the availability of proteins which is under the influence of several factors as described above.

Consider Y_t ; the ARIMA time series of an explanatory variable X_t is written as a linear transfer function of a series of noises:

$$Y_t = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \varphi_j \varepsilon_{t-j} \quad (1)$$

Mathematically, the equation of this model is as follows:

$$Y_t = c + \varphi_1 Y_{t-1} + \varphi_2 Y_{t-2} + \dots + \varphi_p Y_{t-p} + \theta_1 \varepsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \varepsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \varepsilon_{t-q} + \beta X_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

- Y_t is the time series of interest at time t , which in this case represents the availability of animal proteins per day per individual.
- c is a constant term.
- $\varphi_1; \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_p$ represent the autoregressive coefficients, respectively, at one, two, ... and p offset. These coefficients measure the correlation between observations at different time lags.
- $Y_{t-1}, Y_{t-2}, \dots, Y_{t-p}$ are the lagged values of the time series.
- $\theta_1; \theta_2, \dots, \theta_q$ are the moving average coefficients.
- $\varepsilon_{t-1}, \varepsilon_{t-2}, \dots, \varepsilon_{t-q}$ are the autoregressive error terms. Each represents the residual error or noise at a previous time ($\varepsilon_t \varepsilon_{t-i}$) in the ARIMA model. These terms capture the residuals unexplained by the autoregressive model.
- β is the coefficient of the explanatory variable X_t .
- X_t is the value of the explanatory variable at time t .
- ε_t is the white noise error term at time t .

- p represents the number of autoregressive terms in the ARIMA model.
- q represents the number of moving average terms in the ARIMA model.

To obtain a forecast Y_{t+L} (L denoting an upcoming year or time lag) of the explanatory variable X , the following equation was used (Saki, 2016):

$$Y_t = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \varphi_j \varepsilon_{t-j} \quad (2)$$

As part of this study, the forecasts for the availability of animal proteins at individual level by 2030 were made under the influence of various parameters considered, in particular: precipitation, temperature, CH₄, CO₂, N₂O, the price per ton, the annual crude income, agricultural area, population density, total production, and change in stocks. These various analyses were carried out using R version 4.3.0 software and Excel was used to enter the data obtained from the two sources (World Bank and FAO websites).

Results

Chronological Evolution of the Main Parameters

Chronological Evolution of Rainfall

Figure 2 (Appendix) shows the temporal history of precipitation and temperature in Turkey during the period from 1990 to 2020. From a climatic point of view, we initially observe irregular fluctuations characterized by random variations which do not follow a predictable or regular pattern for both precipitation and temperature. Indeed, although there are strong variations in time of these climatic parameters, the evolution of the average annual rainfall and especially of the temperature clearly indicates general upward trends in Turkey. Thus, from 11 °C in 1990, the temperature in Turkey is around 13 °C in 2020, an increase of 2 °C in 30 years.

Similarly, although the trend of rising temperatures is clearly more observed, it is also observed that rainfall has tended to increase slightly over the past thirty years in Turkey. This makes it possible to understand that this country, like the Asian continent taken as a whole, is confronted with several extremely serious climatic situations, among which are global warming and floods. Thus, nearly a hundred or precisely 81 meteorological disasters were observed on this continent in 2022, with the majority (83%) linked to floods and storms, resulting in several thousand deaths. It is important to specify that these increases observed for the two parameters could accentuate the mortality rate in animals.

Chronological Evolution of Atmospheric Pollutants

The evaluation of the evolution of air pollutants is also part of the analysis of the situation of Turkey in the context of climate change and its impact on the availability of protein of animal origin. Figure 3 (Appendix) shows the chronological evolution of three atmospheric pollutants including methane (CH₄), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and nitrous oxide (N₂O).

The analysis of this figure shows a trend towards a strong increase in the quantity of these three pollutants over the last thirty years. Indeed, from 2000 kt of methane in 1990, the situation is more and more alarming in this country with a total quantity exceeding 4500 kt in 2020, a rate of increase of 125% of CH₄. Concerning nitrous oxide (N₂O), from around 100 kt (1990), the quantity of this pollutant has increased to around 220 kt in 2020. The situation is even more worrying regarding carbon emissions (CO₂) where we observe an increase of more than 300,000 kt between 1990–2020.

Moreover, the increase in these pollutants, in particular, CH₄ and N₂O, in this country remains consistent with the general situation observed on the Asian continent where anthropogenic activities, in particular, agricultural production, dominate. Thus, all these increases in the various pollutants truly explain the global warming observed globally in general and in Turkey in particular. Their contribution to the problem of global warming indirectly makes these pollutants factors that can promote an increase in the mortality rate in animals and therefore elements whose increase would favor a reduction in animal production.

Total Population over Time

Figure 4 shows the chronological evolution of the size of the total population in Turkey from 1990 to 2020. As in most countries of the world, there is an increasing evolution of the population density within this country during this time interval. Indeed, from a density of about 55 million inhabitants in 1990, Turkey recorded in 2020 an increase of almost 65% in the size of its population to reach an active population of more than 85 million inhabitants. In addition, the population explosion in this country is placing strong pressure both on food resources (especially animal proteins) and on those used for their production such as land and agricultural production inputs.

Figure 4. Chronological Evolution of the Total Population in Turkey between 1990–2020

Chronological Evolution of the Total Agricultural and Pasture Area

The influence of the demographic explosion observed previously is not without effect on resources, on the occupation of the territory, and the use of the resources which accompany it. Indeed, Figure 5 (Appendix) shows the evolution over time of the areas occupied for agricultural production and those reserved for pasture (permanent and temporary) in Turkey between 1990 and 2020. The analysis of this figure indicates a downward trend in agricultural production areas ranging from over 39.5 million hectares (1990) to around 37.5 million hectares (2020).

Regarding the areas of permanent and temporary pasture, there is an increasing and gradual evolution over time in this country. These results testify to the growing interest of most producers in adapting to agropastoral techniques and to urban grazing. Nevertheless, even if the grazing areas are gradually

increasing, the agricultural areas remain larger than those exploited for livestock activities. This seems logical especially in a country recognized as one of the pillars of agriculture worldwide. With the gradual reduction of agricultural land, the country could be more vulnerable to the problem of feeding farm animals, especially since it is accepted that products from agricultural land are mainly used to feed farm animals. However, with the expansion of grazing areas nationwide, this lack of feed for farm animals could be compensated by grazing activities.

Chronological Evolution of Economic Indicators

Figure 6 shows the evolution of the annual gross income per capita in Turkey between 1990 and 2020. As for most countries in the world, the analysis of this figure indicates an increasing dynamic of this economic indicator over the last thirty years. During this observation period, the average per capita income evolved from USD 4000 (1990) to USD 12,000 (2013) and is then estimated at around USD 9000 in 2020.

This increase in purchasing power is considered an essential element in access to proteins of animal origin in a context where the consumption of animal proteins is also linked to the standard of living characterized above all by the average income of the population.

Figure 6. Chronological Evolution of Annual Gross Income per Capita in Turkey

Over the past thirty years, the study shows a gradual increase in the price of animal protein (Figure 7). This trend suggests an economic dynamic that deserves special attention. It should be noted that, although this indicator has seen a successive decline over the past five years (from 2015 to 2020), this relatively short period cannot necessarily be interpreted as a long-term trend reversal.

Figure 7. Evolution of the Average Annual Price per Ton of Protein of Animal Origin

Evolution of Protein Availability Indicators in Turkey

Although the purchasing power and price of proteins of animal origin are decisive in the consumption of these proteins, considering the indicators characterizing their production and their accessibility also remains the basis of the degree of availability of these proteins. First, among these indicators, we distinguish the total amount of animal protein produced at the national level. Then, the evolution of the stock, and then the main response variable characterized by the quantity of protein (in grams) available or accessible to all, considering the population density, represent the last two parameters. Indeed, the chronological projection of these three previously listed parameters makes it possible to assess not only the level of overall production of these proteins at the national level (Figure 8 - Appendix).

To this end, graph (a) indicates an increasing evolution of the production of animal proteins during the ten years of observation. Thus, from a production of less than 4 million tons of animal protein in 2010, ten years later, Turkey produced more than 5.7 million tons (i.e., a growth rate of approximately 42%).

Following this increase in total production, graph (b) also shows an increase in the amount of protein available to everyone over the period 2010–2020. From less than 17 g/person/day (2010), Turks had access to more than 19.5 g/day of animal protein in 2020. However, graph (c) shows a stable trend of animal protein stock levels over the past ten years, with values close to zero. This reflects the fact that the increase in production and availability observed at the level of individuals does not sufficiently meet the total demand at the national level.

Prediction of Protein Availability by 2030 in Turkey

Prediction of the Evolution of the Availability of Animal Protein under the Effect of Each Climatic Parameter

Figure 9 shows the annual predictions up to 2030 of the amount of animal protein that would be available to an individual in Turkey under the influence of rainfall, temperature, and atmospheric pollutants such as CO₂ and N₂O.

Analysis of these predictions suggests a gradual decrease in the amount of animal protein that would be available to each individual as we progress from year to year. Thus, the increase in these different climatic

parameters would increasingly lead to a drop in the quantity of protein on a national scale to an even lower threshold compared to that of 2010 (less than 17 g/person/day). Thus, if these parameters continue to increase at the national level as observed over the past thirty years, the forecasts obtained could be verified, thus resulting in low accessibility of animal proteins for the Turkish population in the coming years. It would be interesting to encourage and actively support the transition from fossil energy sources to renewable energies such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, and geothermal energy. Also, on the agricultural level, it would be useful to promote new agricultural methods that preserve the soil, improve carbon sequestration, and reduce the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides. This will contribute to mitigating global warming while strengthening the resilience of agricultural systems to the impacts of climate change. Improving carbon sequestration and reducing the use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides will contribute to mitigating global warming while strengthening the resilience of agricultural systems to the impacts of climate change.

Figure 9. Prediction of the Availability of Animal Proteins under the Effect of Climatic Parameters

Prediction under the Influence of Economic Parameters, Demographics, and Animal Production Indicators

The forecasts were also made by fixing the other parameters considered in this study, in particular the evolution of the price of these animal proteins, the purchasing power of the population (gross annual income per inhabitant), the agricultural areas, the density of population, total animal protein production, and inventory change (Figure 10 - Appendix).

Along with the previous predictions, it seems that only the total domestic production (in tons) will drive the increase in animal protein availability in Turkey over the next ten years. This assumes that the quantity of these proteins will continue to grow to meet the demand of a growing population like that of Turkey, recognized as a high-density country.

On the other hand, all other factors will negatively influence the availability of animal protein in Turkey in the coming years. The evolution of the price of animal proteins implies a strong demand for limited supplies at the national level and even an increase in purchasing power (income) would not be high enough to allow individuals to appropriate animal proteins. This is undoubtedly what explains the negative effect that demography would have on this availability over the next ten years when the country will experience an increase in terms of the number of inhabitants at the national level.

Concerning the negative influence of the stock of animal proteins despite the increase in production, we can therefore deduce that the country would turn more towards the export of these products to revive the national economy, which is currently facing real problems such as the devaluation of the Turkish currency.

Global Prediction of Animal Protein Availability under the Influence of All Observation Parameters

Figure 11 presents the average annual forecasts of the quantity of animal proteins resulting from the various forecasts previously described for the horizon 2030. Indeed, as suggested by most of the previous forecasts, the forecasting model indicates a decreasing trend over time for the next ten years (on the horizon 2030) under the influence of different explanatory parameters. According to these forecasts, the quantity of protein at the level of individuals could decrease to less than 15 g/day if the climatic (temperature, precipitation, pollutants), economic (prices and income), social (demography), and production (quantity produced) and stocks) continue with the same rate of change. Moreover, considering the average weight of men (84 kg) and women (75 kg) in this country, it would take at least 67.2 g/day and 60 g/day of protein, respectively, for men and women. (75 kg). This indicates that neither Turkish women nor Turkish men will have the minimum amount of protein required if they have to settle for animal protein only from the seeds of crops such as: lupine, beans, lentils, chickpeas and many others.

Figure 11. Annual Forecasts for 2030 of the Quantity of Animal Protein Available

Discussion

Turkey, like the rest of the world, faces climate variability characterized mainly by global warming due to a considerable increase in temperature (UN, 2022). Indeed, the upward trend in precipitation and temperatures observed confirms the results of several other works which have highlighted the concern about global warming in the face of the significant increase in temperature over time (Meseguer-Ruiz, & Olcina Cantos, 2023). And the situation could get worse with a 93% chance of experiencing the hottest year on record between 2022 and 2026 (WMO, 2022). Consequently, this increase in the two parameters, particularly concerning temperature, could promote heat stress in animals and therefore increase the mortality rate in certain species (Diallo, Barry, & Weibigue, 2021). In addition, the results of the study indicate that the country is also facing a considerable increase in atmospheric pollutants (CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O). Indeed, Turkey is among the top 10 nations in the world and first at the European level in terms of level of agricultural production over the past decade. However, it has been recognized that agricultural practices, including fertilizer use and runoff, are the source of the emission of these pollutants through the process of nitrogen release to the environment and decomposition of manure (UN, 2022). However, the increase in CO₂ in this country is associated with the development of industrial activities in Asia (Ali, et al., 2022).

The evaluation of population density made it possible to confirm also in this country the persistence of the phenomenon of demographic explosion observed in the whole world (Rosenthal, 2011). Indeed, with an increase of nearly 65% in the size of its population in 2020 compared to that of 1990, Turkey is considered the 18th most populous country in the world according to the Ministry of Europe and Foreign Affairs (MEFA, 2023).

This demographic explosion accentuates the pressure around resources, in particular, land, with a strong urbanization of Turkish society in recent years (Serttaş, 2010), leading to a reduction in agricultural production spaces following their depletion over time. Likewise, this continuous increase in the Turkish population is considered a determining factor in the insufficient availability of these resources, in terms of proteins of animal origin (Caillavet, Fadhuile, & Nichèle, 2019).

However, the results of the analyses showed an increase in pasture areas, in terms of the area occupied by livestock. This demonstrates the importance of the breeding system in this country. Indeed, projects have been carried out in the sense of the promotion of pastoral cultures through, for example, a development of the Hevsel gardens as reported in Thevenin, (2015). It is in this sense that Larrière, (2019) evokes the growing interest in agro-pastoral techniques with urban pastures, entering above all into the scheme of development projects aimed at both rural and urban areas (Thevenin, 2015). These projects have enabled this country to position itself 6th in the world in terms of animal production, particularly sheep (268,000 tons per year), and in terms of sheep's milk production.

From an economic point of view in relation to proteins of animal origin, it appears that the country is facing an increase in the price per ton of these proteins, also considering the context of the general inflation that the country has been experiencing for several years (Reuters, 2022). Thus, according to the Statistical Institute of Turkey, the country has experienced a record in terms of inflation with an annual rate of around 86%, thus leaving poor or precarious households with a monthly income of less than 5500 Turkish liras (TL) (less than 300 euros/month) (Reuters, 2022). This growing inflation around animal protein with such a low annual income explains the low consumption of protein of animal origin compared to the world average consumption, regarding meat, eggs, and other proteins of animal origin (Gürer, 2021).

However, incomes are also on the rise, thus characterizing the improvement of their purchasing power thanks to the main investments which are increasingly made at the level of Asia (UNCTAD, 2021). Concerning the production of proteins of animal origin, the results from the FAO data showed an

increasing evolution of the number of tons produced during the ten years of observation, this to meet a demand that increases with the size of the population (OECD/FAO, 2021). In addition to this increase, there is also an increasing availability of animal protein at the level of individuals at the national level. This speed of production follows that observed at the global level, where global meat production also increased by 45% in 2020 compared to production in 2000 (Tüfekci, 2023). But despite these increases, stock analysis indicates a stable trend over the last ten years of assessment. This thus testifies to the fact that the production of animal proteins in Turkey is still insufficient in the face of the total demand at the national level, especially in a country considered to be part of the top 20 most populated countries (MEFA, 2023).

General forecasts suggest that under the influence of climatic (temperature, pollutants), social (demography), and economic (prices and income) parameters, as well as the level of animal protein production, the availability of proteins at the level of individuals will change and be regressive over the next ten years. This would be logical in the sense that the decisive influence of the sharp increase in these parameters, in particular temperature and atmospheric pollutants, on the livestock sector has been highlighted by several authors (Diallo, Barry, & Weibigue, 2021). The forecast model indicates a daily availability of less than 15 g/person if the effects of climate change and the demographic explosion continue to be felt at the national level. However, the minimum need of the inhabitants of this country in terms of protein is estimated at approximately 67 g/day and 60 g/day, respectively, for men and women, according to their average weight (World Data, 2020) and the recommended minimum amount of protein per kg of body weight (Tüfekci, 2023; Bilodeau, 2018).

Faced with this concern, some suggest developing other food products with substitute proteins, in particular vegetable proteins from legume seeds (PNNS, 2017). To these proteins are added other proposals such as proteins from oilseeds (soya, sunflower, rapeseed, peanuts, etc.) and cereals (wheat, millet, oats, rice), all considered to be the main sources of vegetable proteins (Cuq, 2018).

In addition, the demand around these vegetable proteins is increasing more and more today, with the increase in population density and the evolution of dietary patterns towards vegetarian diets (Mordor Intelligence, 2021).

Nevertheless, it would be more interesting to also strengthen food policies favorable both to research and innovation in the livestock and fishing sector, as well as to the protection of natural resources with a view to creating an environment conducive to a responsible increase in animal protein production. This in a context where, although substitute proteins of plant origin constitute an interesting strategy, it is accepted that 42% of the amount of protein consumed daily should be of animal origin (Tüfekci, 2023).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study highlight the challenges that Turkey faces due to global warming, population explosion, and economic constraints that influence the availability of animal protein in the country. Indeed, the results of this study indicate that, like other countries in the world, Turkey is facing climate change characterized by a significant increase in temperatures and atmospheric pollutants, thus leading to an increase in the frequency of meteorological disasters, such as floods and storms.

These results testify to the need to find an adequate formula aimed at mitigating this general situation. Furthermore, despite an increase in the areas occupied by farm animals, the production of animal proteins remains insufficient and faces growing demand from the Turkish population, which at the same time continues to grow considerably. Add to this, the inflation observed for several years in this country does not leave the livestock sector on the sidelines, with the increase in the price of animal proteins a determining factor in access to these essential sources of nutrition.

Future predictions underscore the need for action to address the challenges associated with a likely decrease in the amount of protein at the level of individuals in this country. In addition to the development of food products with alternative proteins, it is crucial to strengthen food policies that promote research, innovation, and the protection of natural resources in the livestock and fisheries sector. These proposed solutions aim to improve the availability of animal proteins sustainably and responsibly while considering environmental and social issues. A balanced and concerted approach between government actors, farmers, herders, and civil society is essential to address this challenge and ensure the food and nutrition security of the Turkish population in the years to come.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, K.E.T. and Y.E.M.; methodology, S.A.; validation, Y.E.M. and K.F.D.; formal analysis, K.F.D.; investigation, and resources, K.E.T.; data curation, Y.E.M., K.F.D. and S.A.; writing—original draft preparation, K.E.T., Y.E.M., S.A. and K.F.D.; writing—review and editing, Y.E.M. and K.F.D.; visualization, K.E.T. and S.A.; supervision, S.A.; project administration, K.E.T. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Figure 2. Chronological Evolution of Rainfall and Temperature between 1990–2020

Figure 3. Chronological evolution of atmospheric pollutants (CH₄, CO₂ and N₂O)

Figure 5. Chronological Evolution of Agricultural and Pasture Area

a

b

c

Figure 8. Chronological Evolution of the Quantity of Total Production and of the Stock Variation of Animal Proteins. (a) indicates an increasing evolution of the production of animal proteins during the ten years of observation, (b) also shows an increase in the amount of protein available to everyone over the period 2010–2020, (c) shows a stable trend of animal protein stock levels over the past ten years, with values close to zero.

Figure 10. Prediction under the Effect of Economic Parameters, Demography, and Animal Production Indicators

